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**THE SOCIO-LINGUISTICS OF FAMILY LANGUAGE PRACTICES AMONG
SELECTED EDUCATED FAMILIES IN JOS, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

Scholars have focused more attention on national language policy, while language practices by individuals and families has not received so much attention. On a macro level, language policy involves a political decision and a deliberate attempt to change/influence/affect the various aspects of language practices and the status of one or more languages in a given society and it can be articulated, for instance, in official state documents, that establish a country's official language. Language practices are observable language behaviors and language choices occurring in social interaction which provide a context for language use and language learning and are influenced by a group's or an individual's (language) ideologies. Since the field of language planning and language policy blossomed, literature in the past sixty (60) years has largely been on macro language planning. This study is a modest attempt to shift the focus and also shed the light on micro planning in this part of the world. Multiple theories abound to explain micro language practices such as Fishman's Reversing Language Shift Model and Spolsky's Family Language Policy Model. This study has adopted both which present a guiding tool for exploring the families' language policies through the exploration of three particular topics: their language beliefs, their language practices, and their planning efforts to maintain and develop languages as used in the environments they reside. The study employs a structured questionnaire. Data obtained is analyzed qualitatively. The major finding reveals that families of educated urban dwellers do not have a planned family language. Other findings show that the knowledge, situation, motivation and critical awareness are responsible for this situation.

Keywords: family language planning, language planning, language policy, language management and language behaviour and sociolinguistics

Introduction

The present study aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of family language practices with a focus on their daily interactions. Nigeria is a country characterized by multilingualism. The use of more than two languages by citizens is common place. The situation is not peculiar to Nigeria, as it is also noticeable in other parts of the world. A family with heritage language can therefore be found to be using another language. This situation is a norm on the African continent because of the multiplicity languages and the lack of a shared common language. Although studies in family language planning abound in the European Union (Chatzidaki, A. & Maligkoudi, C. 2013 and Bezcioglu-Goktolga, I. & Yagmur, K. 2018), not the same can be said of Africa in general and Nigeria in particular. This investigation therefore adds to literature. The point has to be made clear at this initial stage that it excludes those of hard of hearing. Cooper (1989) and Spolsky (2004) have challenged scholars in the field of language planning and language policy to shift from the macro aspects of national/state planning and focus more on micro planning in order to understand the language behaviour and management in the society. Blommaert (2018) has drawn the attention of scholars in the field of language planning about the shift and attributed it to the failure of macro language planning to account for actual language practices. This study is therefore a modest attempt to respond to the challenge that has been established. Contributions of the early scholars in the field of language planning have remained significant and responsible for the growth that have been witnessed in the history of the field. Specific mention of Haugen's (1959) classical study which investigated the ecology of languages was more descriptive in nature. Renewed interests in the field of language planning and policy (LPP) has ensured that it has moved from a mere descriptive study to becoming more theoretical, predictive and explanatory (Hornberger 2006). Since Haugen spearheaded the field, other scholars came up with definitions at the infancy stage which focused more on government or its agencies carrying out the tasks of planning language for various reasons such as altering language behaviour for a specific group of people (Neustupny 1983; Weinstein 1980; Karam 1974; Tauli 1974; Fishman 1974; Das Gupta 1973). It becomes clear that these three components are at the heart of macro language planning. Unions of countries can also constitute agents that formulate the language behaviour of the countries that are members of such a union. For example, Wiertelwska (2012) notes that the European Union is an example of an agent of LPP. People migrate to different parts of the world for various reasons and they are confronted with the reality of new languages. Interaction in the new environment is inevitable and they therefore add one or more languages that exist there into their repertoire.

Aim and objectives

Families like to maintain their language, but they also need to keep up with the expectations of society. The aim of this investigation is to investigate these contradictions. Implicitly or explicitly, families build their own language policies. Through these policies, families aim to bring up children in their language. Depending on the characteristics of each family, families might have different language policies. For instance, in a family where the first language of the mother and the father are different, a neutral language can be adopted. Based on the issues referenced in the introduction above, the objectives of this investigation is to

1. Understand how multilingualism affects families' language policy
2. The role of the society as it influences the use of multiple languages
3. The part individuals play as agents in the introduction of other languages into the family.

Statement of the problem

The use of a heritage language in a family necessitates the maintenance of culture in such a family. This is the ideal situation where the parents share the same language. In this circumstance, they are able to transmit the language to their children. When there is more than one language in a family, it is often a point of discussion what language to use. Families of educated urban dwellers do not seem to have a planned family language. Language usage in the family ranges from explicit and overt to unplanned and unconscious. And it's rarely rigid because both the children and the family are socially connected and everything around them is changing all the time. This condition arises as a result of the knowledge, situation, context, motivation and critical awareness of the various languages they use. We recommend that scholars embark on extensive investigations to understand reasons for such language behaviour.

Research questions

The study adopts a qualitative method of data collection in order to provide answers the following research questions:

1. How does multilingualism affect family language planning (FLP)?
2. What are the tensions arising from the environment on FLP?
3. What role does agency play in revealing unknown languages in the family?

Significance of the study

This investigation will impact the academic discipline as well as stakeholders and user communities. It contributes to the development of the research subfield of FLP by advancing

concrete knowledge on variations in specific communities. Furthermore, it contributes to the field of early multilingual acquisition by providing much needed information on input factors that drive multilingual development. The body of new knowledge on FLP generated is likely to have significant impact on policy and practice. An understanding of the interrelationships between multilingual practices and identity construction can facilitate an appreciation by wider society of the benefits of multilingualism and what it means to be a contemporary citizen. The investigation aims to provide knowledge to multilingual, transcultural families and communities themselves will gain from this research by learning from each other about effective multilingual communicative strategies in the family domain, which will in turn promote social well-being in multilingual development.

Literature review

Language planning and policy has caught the attention of nations and organizations in terms of the language(s) chosen and promoted for official functions. Initially known as *language engineering*, language planning began in Europe following the disintegration of European nations which led to the emergence of nation states in Africa and Asia especially for the adoption of a national language- what is called *one language model* (Baldauf 2012: 234). Various organizations around the world have contributed to development of language policies in these African and Asian countries (Kaplan 2003, 2010; Nekvapil 2011; Ricento 2011). Early scholars in the field portrayed the impression that adopting a linguistic change was a catalyst for development and modernization, an idea that was largely accepted by the nations (Baldauf, 2012).

Haugen (1966) remains the arrowhead that other scholars have emulated to understand who? what? why? and how? languages are planned and the policies that eventually emerge from the planning. For him, the focus is on four categories which are norm selection, codification, elaboration and implementation. It becomes apparent that making decisions is germane given the number of languages that exist in a given country, especially in Africa where the countries are highly multilingual. The governments in these countries are faced with this challenge in order to ensure integration, learning and communication among other reasons (Appel and Muyskeen 1987). One of the early proponents in the field, Fishman (1973), defines language planning as a ‘set of deliberate activities systematically designed to organize and develop the language resources of the community in an ordered schedule of time’. A cursory look into the definition of language planning suggests that LP is viewed from the perspective of corpus and status planning. According to Fishman, the point of conflict is in status planning, and it manifests itself in inter-ethnic skirmishes just as it is the area where there are rewards (Fishman 1997b).

Baldauf (2006) argues that for some time, attention in language planning had been on macro sociolinguistics and this has remained so for a while. This is because of the factor of agency that rests on government as the main actors in the field. He goes further to argue that language planning involves the activities and processes leading to the promulgation of a language policy by the government of a country or a person. For Kaplan & Baldauf (1997), they view language policies as bodies of ideas, laws, regulations, rules and practices intended to achieve some planned language change.

A large number of definitions have been provided by scholars as to what language planning means. On the whole, LP is a deliberate attempt by authorities to regulate and determine how the languages that exist in a given society are used by the citizens. Haugen (1966) argues that LPP can be viewed as treating language as a problem. This is why Spolsky (2004) notes that language and the policies that are eventually made about them are multifaceted. According to him, language policies can be implicit or explicit. He goes further to state that in some countries, even though the policy is not explicit, the nature of the policy is derived from the language practices of the citizens. For Kaplan and Baldauf (1997), they see LPP as a body of ideas and regulations put in place with the intention to achieve a deliberate action in the use of the languages that exist in a given context. They go further to explain that LPP modifies the behaviour of the people in a society for some reasons which can be at the macro and micro levels. At the macro stage, the government is involved and the intention could be to modernize, standardize or unify the languages. Micro planning focuses on specific and limited language issues. Language planning at the micro level have not received so much as planning at the macro level probably because of prestige (Kaplan and Baldauf 1997). It becomes apparent that there are several factors that influence planning at different levels. Williams (1994) lists some of the factors at the micro level to include educational opportunities through the medium of English, residential mobility, socioeconomic and class consciousness, language switching and language loss and inter-ethnic marriage patterns among others.

On his part, Kennedy (1982) views language planning as the deliberate changes in the form or use of languages which are socially-based. He also recognizes that planning can take place at the macro and micro levels just as Kaplan & Baldauf (1994) have done above. Weinstein (1980) views language planning as an activity authorized and undertaken by the government that is long-term, sustained with conscious efforts to distort the functions of the languages that exist in a given society with the purpose of solving a communication challenge. Two things stand out from this definition: the political aspect and communication problems. Similarly, Jernudd & Das Gupta (1971) insist on the political aspect and communication problems. Rubin (1973) views language planning as a means of solving mechanism for anticipated (future-oriented) problems that

languages will bring if not planned. She goes a step further to say that when this happens, there will be goals and alternatives at every stage of the planning. In their submission, Das Gupta & Ferguson (1977) liken planning language as the allocation of resources to the various sectors with the hope of an expected outcome and objectives. For them, language planning involves assigning functions to the various languages and developing their use. Cooper (1979) also belongs to this School of thought consider language as a resource.

A language policy therefore denotes the habitual language practice of a given speech community which selects a particular variety or varieties for use by the people (Spolsky and Shohamy, 2000). It is for this reason that Spolsky and Shohamy (2000) argue that a given language policy is influenced by the society's language ideology, which is their belief and influences what they practice with the designated language. They note that a language policy can sometimes be found in different documents, other times, it is difficult to locate. Those visible and easy to locate might include official documents such as those in a national constitution, language law or a cabinet document. These kinds of policies are clear-cut and are therefore not hard to locate (Spolsky and Shohamy, 2000). Language policies that are clearly defined become obvious. As language policies influence the speech behaviour of people, the speakers of the chosen code(s) are guided and their actions determined by the language policy. This explains why the chosen language is jealously guarded by the policy-makers, usually, the elite to guide and determine present and future decisions. The factor of integration takes the center stage in countries in Africa such as South Africa, Somalia, Tanzania and Nigeria among many others that are faced with the problem of multilingualism (cf. Ojo 2010; Adegbija 2007).

Baldauf (2006:154-5) believes that agency plays a very vital role in micro language planning, more than it does in macro language planning. According to him, the importance of agency in micro language planning lies in the fact that individuals and groups create a genuine language policy by planning, utilizing and developing their language resources according to their needs, 'language problems', and requirement for language management. Neustupny & Nekvapil (2003) cited in Baldauf (2006) describe families as units of micro language planning where the users of languages are the planning agents. Agency therefore resides squarely with the family members in this kind of planning. We find the submission instrumental and useful in this investigation because we are interested in the language problems and language management of educated urban dwellers in Nigeria.

Family language planning is a thriving and blooming field of inquiry. Investigations into family language planning are few and far between as Cooper (1989:37-38) has accused scholars

in the field language of showing little interest in micro language planning. Interestingly, he reveals that it is wrong to study language planning at only the macro level. The implication of his assertion is that the approach should be bottom-top and not the reverse.

King, Fogle, & Logan-Terry (2008) see FLP as the overt and explicit planning of language use in the home by family members. Their position is similar to that of Spolsky (2012b), who reveals that FLP occurs at the family level as it is an integral part of the community, neighbourhood, and workplace among many others. Families devise techniques of dealing with the multiplicity of languages around them. This is because the heritage language of families are jeopardized as a result. What usually happens is that the dominant language of the community ‘swallows’ the smaller ones, thus forcing families to partially or completely their first language and also making children to become bilinguals of various degrees. Zhao (2018) reveals that so much has been written and investigated at the macro and meso strata of language planning and calls for concerted efforts to research into what he calls the miniaturization, individualization and localization planning. It will seem like Zhao’s appeal has been heeded by Barkhuizen & Knoch (2006), Baldauf (2006) and Canagarajah (2005) who have further studied and improved this type of language planning. What then is family language planning and why is it important? Globalization has been largely responsible for the promotion of international languages, English, for example, for international relations, trade, and communication. Consequently, nations and their citizens have yielded to the phenomenon of globalization with the attendant problem of neglecting smaller languages. In other words, in the family setting, the members are the agents for the diffusion of a particular language or multiple languages as the case may be. Within the family therefore, micro language planning is not sponsored by the government but activated and encouraged by the members (Brann 2010).

Like any thriving field or subfield, its development is recorded in phases. It is for this reason that Wang and Yang (2022:15-16) remind us that the development FLP can be broadly divided into four phases. They argued that these phases are: phase 1 focused on classic diaries in which researchers documented children’s development; phase 2 dwelt on the difference between bilingual and monolingual learners in their language development trajectories; phase 3 started around the 2000s and focused on language use as a social practice in bilingual and multilingual families and phase 4 commenced around 2010 and is concerned on examining language competence as a means to defining the roles of parents and children in family life. The chronology, indeed, is a useful barometer for researchers in FLP on where to concentrate their energies. The sub-field FLP developed at different points in time in different countries. In China it is recent and

began in the 21st century focused on minority ethnic families that are multilingual as well as non-ethnic but multilingual families (Wang & Yang, 2022:16).

The use of different languages at different places, otherwise known as domain, has captured the attention of sociolinguists over time. There is a link between macro and micro language management based on the domain of usage (Fishman 1972). It is for this reason that Spolsky (2004:43) argues that at the family level, the policy can be analyzed as the practice, ideology and language management. According to him, the choice of a language (which is practice) is influenced by proficiency in the language, desire to gain advantage and the desire to get advantage by obliging to the wishes of the audience. This informs why Rizki & Fajri (2021) explored how children actively influence family language practices in French-Rwandan Kinyarwanda families living in Belgium.

Scholars have defined family language planning in many varied ways. Zhao (2018:528) looks at family language planning as “plans and ideas that affect the language use of family members”. It will suggest that a family which plans its language practice purposefully decides on a particular language that is understood by the parents, children and perhaps other relations for the purpose of communication among them. This definition also affirms the multiplicity of languages and the decision to settle on a particular medium when they need to interact. Although on the surface this looks seamless and easy, the challenge becomes real and glaring when the parents do not speak the same language as a result of inter-ethnic marriages, socio economic status and area of residence (cf. Williams 1994). In other words, communication challenges arise in real discourse, when people engage in conversation (Neustupny 1983). The challenge is glaring when the people involved in a communication do not use the same language. The language practice of a family determines how such a family plans the usage of languages at its disposal. It is for this reason that scholars in the field regard family language planning as the foundation of language planning (Zhao 2018, Baldauf 2006, and Canagarajah 2005). Regrettably, scholars have also identified the negligence of family language planning investigations as researching it would provide the needed support in the area of language planning (Wiley & Wright 2004, Robinson & Richard Brecht 2006).

Family language is important for several reasons. Zhao (2018: 528-9) has argued that one of these reasons include solving societal language problems. It means that when families encounter differences in language of communication, a common language is then adopted to facilitate interaction. Secondly, family language facilitates language acquisition in children. Parents are able to determine which language their children in order of preference. This is particularly important

for families in multilingual settings. For such families, a conscious attempt is made about learning and speaking the various languages with their children. Parents that are multilingual can decide to use a particular language to their children at home and another language when they are outside the home. By engaging in the use of various languages, the parents plan the family's language policy (cf. Spolsky 2004:43). Thirdly, family language planning encourages language identification among families. Where the parents in a given family share a common first language, there is a possibility that it is the language that family will identify as its heritage language. The situation however changes when either of the parents share different languages, it becomes difficult for them to identify a common language for usage among the children. For Spolsky (2004:43), another reason he identified for studying family language planning is immigration, whether it is from one country to another or whether it is from one city to another. Extra and Yagmur (2004: 60) have argued that in South Africa, because of its highly diversified linguistic composition, nine languages are constitutionally recognized for usage in that country. They went further to add that 'home language speakers of the nine official African languages jointly constituted approximately two-thirds of the total population of the country'. By this they mean that there are languages used at home by their speakers and there are those that are used in the public space. It therefore suggests that families are multilingual and make the conscious choice of which language to use in the public. The South African perspective gives a fair idea of how families regulate their language usage. A pertinent will naturally arise concerning the agents involved in unraveling the family language policy. Baldauf (2006:154) argues that agency plays a significant role in language planning at the family. By his estimation, the factor of agency is important at the micro level; although he did not concede that it is not important at the macro level. According to him, aside the planning strategy, agency is rated central because the agents are the implementers who are actively involved in the execution. He adds that it is generally acknowledged by scholars in the field that the impact of agency is felt more at the meso and micro levels (Kaplan & Baldauf 2003:201). When agency is central at the micro level, it suggests that the implementation is bottom-top unlike the top-bottom approach in the macro language planning level (Baldauf, 2006:155).

There is a belief that parents are largely responsible for formulating a family's language. However, studies have shown that children are active agents in the formulation and negotiation of family language policies (Luykx 2005). This explains why Kheirkhah (2016) has argued that as a blooming field of research, family language policy is interdisciplinary taking on fields like sociolinguistics, bilingualism and second language acquisition. Managing the language pattern of a family does not come with so much ease as there explicit and implicit codes that are tolerated or not by the parents. This is observable in the language ideology of the family (Spolsky 2008,

Shohamy 2006). Spolsky (2007:4) suggests that there are members of the family observe the implicit rules that encourage appropriate language. Family language planning investigates how parents attempt to maintain the customary language of the family (Spolsky 2012b:7). Several factors are taken into consideration when investigating family language planning, some of which are ideologies, practices and management (Canagarajah 2008:170). Similarly, Blommaert (2018:3) has argued that family language planning is a response to a means of engaging with serious matters of rationalizing language ideologies at the micro level. So, it follows that when families plan and manage their languages, there are expectations parents have about their children's language use and choice (Curdt-Christiansen 2013). Mauziyyah, Setyaningsih & Sumardi (2024) in their study revealed that Indonesian parents view ideology as the strongest reason why their children should learn and use other languages because of the economic, access to global information and cross cultural benefits. Furthermore, Indonesian parents believe that the use of Indonesian mother tongue languages nature the cultural identity of their children, reinforce emotional ties with the family and society, and form a solid foundation for their language and cognitive development.

In this investigation therefore, we draw on the assumption that as a speech community (in our case, the family) has its language policy as espoused by Spolsky (2004, 2009, and 2011), that is dependent on the three factors of *language beliefs*, *language practices*, and *language management*. As families have beliefs, practices and manage their language, the success of such planning come in varying levels or degrees. The submission of King, Fogle & Logan-Terry (2008) will suggest that parents make deliberate and conscious efforts for their children to use and speak the language they feel is best for them. Many a times, the level of success or failure by the children also impacts on the planned family language. According to Kayam & Hirsch (2012b), this is because when these children are growing and interacting with other people in the environment, they disrupt, change and distort the FLP. Curdt-Christensen (2009) has argued that FLP succeeds when there is a consensual ideology that plays a prominent role in the success in the language management. It is important to note that language ideologies and beliefs are the backbone of FLP. The overarching aim of FLP is its contribution to nurturing an all-encompassing and sustainable language education and multilingual development. This has informed our desire to undertake this study.

Theoretical framework

Family language policy (FLP) is about implicit and explicit language planning in the family (Curdt-Christiansen, 2009). It involves family members' linguistic ideologies, practices and management in relation to language preferences and literacy practices (Curdt-Christiansen, 2009;

Spolsky, 2004, 2007). Explicit and covert practices are deliberate and observable efforts of family members, especially parents, for intended linguistic practices, while implicit and covert practices are the natural results of embedded language beliefs (Curdt-Christiansen, 2018). FLP focuses on how families value bi-/multilingualism and how they translate these values into practices in their linguistic experiences in the families, and involves how a society influences and contributes to language policy (Curdt-Christiansen, 2013). FLP research intersects with multiple academic disciplines, including child language acquisition, language policy, language socialization and language ecology (Curdt-Christiansen, 2018; King et al., 2008; Schwartz & Verschik, 2013). Besides all these, FLP is frequently informed by Fishman's Reversing Language Shift Model (Fishman, 1991), since much of the FLP research examines the efforts of the families to maintain an ethnic minority language in the family as well as in the wider community (Schwartz & Verschik, 2013). As Fishman (1991) puts the linguistic interaction between mother and child in the centre of language transmission, which takes place mostly within the family environment, the influence of his model on FLP studies is undeniable. Keeping the contributions of the theories and models mentioned above in mind, I draw this investigation on the theoretical model of Fishman (1991) and Spolsky (2004, 2007). Spolsky defines three components of language policy: language ideologies, language practices and language management. Curdt-Christiansen (2018) places the language components in the centre of FLP. Language ideologies are about beliefs regarding languages and language use. Language practices are about what people choose and use among the varieties of their linguistic repertoire. Language management is any kind of observable effort and intervention to effect actual language practices. Being the cornerstone of FLP, these components influence and are influenced by various intra-family and societal factors. Language socialization and FLP are closely interrelated. Taking educated urban families as an example, family members have their own beliefs and practices for home language use. These beliefs and practices are closely affected by their home environment and parents' background. However, although the family has certain norms and background for language use, it is not an isolated unit from the society. Children go to school, interact in another language; parents go to work, they need to adapt themselves to socialize and to be competent in this outside world. This process of language socialization brings the sociolinguistic environment in the home domain, having a powerful impact on language ideologies, practices and management of a family.

Research Methodology

The participants

The main criterion for selecting the participants for this current study was for the families to have at least two children. The justification for a family having at least two children is that the children interact with other children in school and playgrounds and therefore they pick other languages from their peers. Therefore, the sample population is a family, consisting of a father, mother and children resident in Jos city, central Nigeria. The participating families were selected through random, purposive and snowballing sampling technique (Marczyk, DeMatteo & Festinger 2005; Kazdin, 1992). This kind of sampling enables a researcher to identify the target population with a view of achieving the objective of the study (Palys 1997). The participants were not expected to reveal their identity; therefore, their privacy was maintained (Yin 2011). We were particular about the ages of the respondents going by the constitutional provisions of Nigeria. The Nigerian Constitution (1999) defines a person as an adult having attained the age of 18 years. For such a person (a male), he can contract a valid marriage and in the case of a female, she can be contracted in a marriage.

Quite a number of studies on family language planning have utilized qualitative approach (Extra & Yagmur, 2004; Wang & Curdt-Christiansen, 2017). The aim of this study was to enable us understand how educated families in Jos city utilize the language resources at their disposal for communication within the home and outside. Succinctly, we sought to know from our respondents what common language they have chosen for interaction among themselves.

One hundred (100) questionnaires were distributed to qualified families in different parts of the city. By qualifications, we mean (a) parents (b) who are residing in Jos city and (c) have obtained a university degree or its equivalent in other tertiary institutions of learning. The investigation was conducted only in Plateau North Senatorial District because of its cosmopolitan nature. Its residents include both the indigenous citizens and those who have come to settle there. In addition, we targeted working-class families whose socio-economic status is considered average according to local standards. By local standards, we mean spouses that are gainfully engaged in the civil service, private organizations and companies. The questionnaires were distributed between the months of September and October 2024 by the researcher and through proxies (Bickman & Rog 1998). From the responses, consistent themes emerged. This practice ensures that the themes were not imposed before the data were collected (Guardado 2002).

Results and Discussion

In this part of the investigation, we document the language choices and language use among the selected families. Given the data's selective focus on educated families residing in the urban areas, who have children and whose socio-economic status is considered average, it is impossible

to give an accurate picture of the language practices of all those who live in Jos, Nigeria their socio-economic status notwithstanding, hence the decision to localize the investigation and thereby generalize. Indeed, within the corpus, there are newly introduced languages that families possess which come to bear in communication. Family members have beliefs in the use of certain languages and therefore make deliberate attempts to use such languages in their daily practices (Spolsky 2004).

Demographic information on respondents

A total of 120 questionnaires were distributed purposively to the selected families. Hundred (100) responses were returned, thus giving a response percentage of 83%. The returned questionnaires were checked for completeness and those improperly completed were eliminated from analysis.

The male gender filled the questionnaire more than their female counterparts. Putting it into perspectives, sixty-four (64) males responded by filling the questionnaires while the 36 were filled by the female gender. Currently in Nigeria, the female gender constitutes 50.7% of the total population (worldbank.org, 2024). We believe that the non-reflection of the reality is as a result of the nonchalant attitude of the female gender towards the survey and their insensitivities to issues of languages in Nigeria. The age distribution of the respondents shows that the cohort of the age groups. The obtained figures are not invariance with the population structure of Nigeria (worldbank.org 2024).

Table 1 showing the age groups, numbers and percentages of respondents.

Age group	Number	Percentage
30-40	16	16%
41-50	44	44%
51-60	31	31%
61+	09	9%

The *state of origin* indicates that respondents from Plateau State were more in number (49); others include Kaduna (4), Ogun (4), Abia (4), Anambra (4), Kogi (4), Delta (4), Niger (5), Borno (4), Bauchi (4), Oyo (4), Edo (4) and Nasarawa (6). We had expected representations from nearly all the States of the Federation, but for the unwillingness of some residents. Our desire was for, at least one, family from every state to participate. Regarding educational attainments, only

those who attended and have attained tertiary education participated. It could be a university degree, a polytechnic diploma or its equivalent. On the length of time for their residency in Jos city, the least is 10 years. In our oral, but informal conversation, we gathered there are those who have lived in the city for upward of 40 years and those have lived in Jos all their lives. More than half of the respondents did not migrate to Jos. It means they have been born and brought up in Plateau State. However, there are those who migrated from other parts of the country to where they are currently residing.

Use of multiple languages in the home

Data on the participants' repertoire of languages suggest evidence of multilingualism. Multilinguals switch between languages. Through a constant use of the available languages, they eventually become proficient in the use of the languages (Diamond, 2010). Multilingualism in Nigeria is the norm as there are many languages. Using Africa as a context, Chumbow (2009) argues that the countries are multilingual in varying degrees, but the condition is not a problem. According to him, linguistic tension is reduced when all the languages are allocated functions given the threat of dominance over one another. When these languages are assigned a portfolio, it brings unity and enhances language development. Multilingualism has long fascinated language planners because of the need to assign portfolios to the languages in a given speech communities because every language has a function. For example, language planners are concerned with what people do with the various languages they speak.

Spolsky (2004, 2009, and 2011) remind us that a speech community, in our case, the family, the language policy is dependent on the factors of *language beliefs*, *language practices*, and *language management*. When we take each of them separately, we notice that for a language to be used (spoken), people do have certain beliefs about it, hence the reason to stick to it; such languages also have their practices and people manage them. Clearly, it becomes evident that those who participated in this investigation demonstrated belief, practice and management in the languages they use. This has informed why they are multilingual. From responses gathered, starting with the parents, majority of them do not speak or possess the same first language or mother tongue. This has informed the reason for multilingualism amongst the families in the context of the study and by extension in the country. Martinez (2007) has emphasized the reality

of multilingualism as a universal phenomenon. He reiterates that as physical borders are crumbling and citizens are interacting across geographical boundaries, coupled with universal linguistic rights which gained momentum from the end of the 20th century, there is currently universal support for linguistic diversity. There is no room for dominance, but ways are being sought to share spaces (languages). This is playing out in families as the nucleus of the society.

The multilingual practices of the respondents is a product of the availability of languages that is encapsulated in the multiple languages that abound in Nigeria (Martinez 2007:2). Nigerians are highly mobile. It is commonplace to find citizens who belong to a particular ethnic residing amongst other dominant ethnic groups in different states and regions. This has informed why the spouses in this study speak different languages but are joined in marriage and must communicate. Families that are multilingual represent rich cultures. Multilingualism shows respect and curiosity towards other cultures as it is obtainable in Nigeria. Adekunle (1972) in his classic study assert that social communication in Nigeria seems difficult given the multiplicity of languages, but this assertion is wrong. Adekunle (1972) paints a vivid picture as it relates to our study saying that Nigerian cities are linguistically diversified and it brings about the challenge of interethnic communication caused by multilingualism, of course:

Influence of environment on the use of languages

Closely related to the use of multiple languages at home is the influence of the environment on such languages. There is a nexus between language and the environment in which it is used. It might seem like migrants are the first victims of using the language(s) of their new environment in addition to their heritage language, however, the category of people who relocate from one part of country to another, especially in a multilingual country like Nigeria are also casualties. Questions 5 and 6 on our questionnaire sought to elicit information on how long the respondents have resided in the area of research and whether they have relocated from any region of the country to their current city of residence. The information obtained indicate that a one-third percentage of the respondents had relocated from other parts of the country. This indicates is that they have a new environment in which a ‘new and common’ language is the principal medium of daily interaction amongst the citizens. This suggests that they would be compelled to learn and use the language outside the home. This means that their new environment has added one more language to their linguistic repertoire. The addition of a new language does not end there, chances are that the ‘outside’ language will be introduced into the home. This is where ‘agency’ by any of the parents or chiefly the children, plays that role. This situation is mirrored by Wang & Yang (2022). They found out that children are the agents of introducing a new language into the family especially

through their interactions with other children in school, parks and places of worship. The children become like chameleons, changing to languages to adapt to the environment. Similarly, this does not exclude the parents playing the role of agents.

The environment therefore becomes a gradual positive force and push towards multilingualism in the family. The picture of the impact of the environment becomes glaring when such families travel to their homeland. This implies that a new environment necessitates alternating between languages in the family and creates tension. The environment thus becomes the avenue where minor or hidden languages are revealed in the family as argued by McConnell (2005). According to him, the environment becomes the bastion of hope and “a blessing for minority languages whose activities may be too micro to be affected by macro policies” (2005). Canagarajah (2005b) expands the argument from a pedagogical perspective claiming that there a shift from the usage of target languages to minor languages. We find these submissions necessary here because our respondents are shifting attention from the known to unknown languages as a result of the environment in which they find themselves.

Agency in the revelation of unknown languages

The focus here is on those persons (parents and children) who are agents and also responsible for introducing other languages in the family repertoire. The issue of agency has for some time remained crucial in LPP as this pertains to those who speak the planned or selected languages (Baldauf, 2006). Arising from this, it is imperative to ask the question: who are these agents/actors that influence language in the family? New languages are acquired from different sources. The learning environment becomes the most important environment for acquiring a new code, especially in Africa. English language is largely an acquired and a second language for most Africans. The picture becomes glaring that schools here serve as fertile grounds for grooming actors that will use the language among the pupils and students and also extending the use at various places including the home.

According to Ricento and Hornberger (1996) cited in Baldauf (2006), teachers are the principal agents in the dissemination of new languages. It is imperative to note that in micro language planning, agency plays an important role in the revelation of unknown languages. Our data reveal that over three-quarters of the respondents claimed that their children attend private schools. Private schools in Nigeria practice ‘straight-for-English’ policy where pupils are immersed in English learning from the first day they step their feet in the schools. Parents, both the educated and uneducated in Nigeria prefer such schools because they believe learning in English enhances their chances of upward social mobility. This belief has accelerated the demand

for English-medium schools and consequently provided learners with a new/second language which they in turn introduce to their families. Our findings have also showed that a variety of languages come to play as they are used in different domains. For example, over three-quarters of the respondents reveal that they are not proficient in their Mother Tongue. They also do not share the same language with their spouses. Therefore, they use a common language which is employed to serve as a means of communication in the family. Furthermore, spouses who claimed to belong to the same ethnic group and use the same language as the means of communication at home, they also use other varieties of language. This is exemplified in the language used in preparing children for school, giving directives, explanations, making love, and communicating with neighbors. For children, they become agents of introducing new languages they acquire from their interactions into the family. The multiplicity of languages as used by the respondents is a pointer to the fact that our respondents do not have a specific language they use among themselves. This is caused by the situation and places they find themselves outside the home. This is in turn caused by the fact that the people they come in contact with do not speak the same language as they do. Thus, revealing the unplanned use of languages by families and the multilingual nature of Nigeria.

Conclusion

In this investigation, we raise the issue of new languages as they are used by educated urban dwellers in Nigeria plan their languages. Large scale studies have been undertaken in macro language policy and planning with an ocean of literature on it. However, attention on micro language planning and specifically on family language planning is scanty. There is currently a movement that is heading towards more insights of language planning in the family. According to Caldas, “All meaningful language policy is ultimately played out in the home and family language policy is not consciously planned, but rather has essentially been predetermined by history and circumstances beyond the family’s control (2012) ”. That is to say, family language policy is influenced by many factors, such as political, economic, educational and social factors and it is a dynamic process. The interests are in language ideology, practice and management. Some examples of practices as part of FLP include not only making sure the children have a need to speak the heritage language at home but also other practices such as the parents’ language use in the home and their involvement in creating opportunities and extracurricular activities in the minority or heritage language outside of the home (Kayam & Hirsch, 2012).

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Dear respondent,

I am a school teacher undertaking a research on language practices in families based in Jos. The idea of the research is to investigate how families make use of various languages for communication at home and in their immediate environment. Your identity will not be disclosed and your responses shall be used strictly for this academic exercise. Tick or circle the answer that applies to you. You are also expected to fill in those portions that require you to write out an answer.

1. Gender (sex) (a) Female (b) Male
2. Age (a) 30-40 (b) 41-50 (c) 51-60 (d) 61+
3. Level of education (a) secondary (b) tertiary
4. State of origin-----
5. How long have you lived in Jos? -----
6. Did you migrate from another part of the country/world to Jos? -----
7. What is your mother tongue (the language of your parents/first language)? -----
8. What is the mother tongue of your spouse (husband/wife)? -----
9. What language do you speak at home with your spouse? -----
10. What language do you speak with your children at home? -----
11. Which is the first language your children learned? -----
12. In what language do you pray at home with the family? -----
13. What language do you and your spouse speak at home? -----
14. What language do your children use among themselves in the house? -----
15. What language do and your spouse use to address those relations/dependents living with you? -----
16. In what language do you make love? -----
17. Of all the languages you speak, which will you say you speak dominantly at home? -----
18. What language do you speak when preparing your children for school? -----

19. When you give directives at home, what language do you use? -----
20. What language do you use in giving explanations at home? -----
21. Will you say your children are proficient in their mother tongue? -----
22. In what language do your children speak to you at home? -----
23. Do your children speak to you in a different language when you are in public? -----
24. In what language do your children prefer to respond to you for an assignment given to them? -----
25. What kind of school do your children attend? (a) Public (b) Private?
26. What language do you use with your neighbors who visit you at home? -----
27. What is the order of languages used in your family (a) mother tongue-second language- language of immediate environment (b) second language-language of immediate environment-mother tongue (c) language of immediate environment-second language-mother tongue (d) what is your order?-----
----- (e.g first language = Alago, second language=English, language of immediate environment=Hausa).
28. Do your children find speaking their mother tongue difficult? -----
29. Have you attempted deciding on the language everyone speaks in your family? -----